

1 Identification of concepts of importance for the assessment of internal validity of *in vitro*
2 toxicology studies using a modified Delphi technique

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68 Abstract

69 **Context:** *In vitro* toxicity studies are increasingly being included as evidence in systematic
70 reviews and chemical risk assessments. INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of
71 *in vitro* studies, is under development ~~in a process consisting of four consecutive studies~~. ~~The~~
72 ~~first step~~ [Study One](#) in the creation of INVITES-IN was the development of an “item bank”
73 database of 405 concepts (“items”) of potential relevance for assessing the internal validity of *in*
74 *vitro* toxicity studies. The items were gathered from ~~both~~ focus group [discussions](#) and a
75 purposive literature sample ~~that included one systematic review and study appraisal tools for~~
76 ~~human, animal, and in vitro studies~~. In this paper we present the second ~~step study in~~ the
77 creation of INVITES-IN, i.e. the methods and results for identifying items for consideration when
78 assessing the potential for bias in an *in vitro* study.

79 **Method:** A two-round digital Delphi survey, followed by ~~an~~ online [Delphi panel workshop with](#)
80 [discussions](#) guided ~~discussions~~ [by a moderator](#), was performed. The Delphi participants were
81 experienced with both ~~in~~ *in vitro* models and systematic review methods.

82 **Results:** Fifteen experts completed both Delphi rounds, and thirteen participated in [the guided](#)
83 [Delphi panel discussion workshops](#). Of the 405 items in the bank, [the experts agreed that 372](#)
84 [should be considered were included for consideration](#) when assessing [the](#) potential for bias in
85 an *in vitro* study. [Items gathered from b](#)Both the literature [sources sample](#) and the focus group
86 discussions [\(in of Study One\) contributed with concepts were](#) considered to be important for the
87 assessment of the potential for bias in an *in vitro* study; 83%-100% of the items collected from
88 the [different literature sources sample](#) were identified to be important and 91% (127) of the new
89 items discovered in the focus group discussions [in of Study One](#) were identified to be important.

90 **Discussion:**

91 The 372 retained items will be interpreted into a manageable set of study appraisal criteria and
92 a supporting guidance that will constitute the INVITES-IN study appraisal tool. [In terms of](#)
93 [lessons for tool development](#), [T](#)he high retention of items included in tools designed for
94 assessment of human and animal studies to *in vitro* studies suggests that many [items validity](#)
95 [concepts](#) are generally applicable across multiple study designs. Therefore, tool development
96 processes should benefit from drawing on assessment tools outside the immediate domain of
97 interest. Tool development would also likely benefit from supplementing literature reviews with
98 focus group discussions, as our results demonstrate that the use of focus group discussions
99 with domain experts [in study 1 was was](#) a pragmatic and valuable approach to increasing
100 coverage of items in a tool development process.

101 In conclusion, this study demonstrates the value of using rigorous methods to ensure a
102 comprehensive dataset as the starting point for creation of an assessment tool, [though the](#)
103 [direct application of Delphi methods to item banks may be an unnecessary step in tool](#)
104 [development](#).

105 1 Introduction

106 Systematic reviews have become increasingly common in toxicology, environmental health, and
107 chemical risk assessment (Menon et al., 2022). Applying systematic review principles in
108 chemical risk assessment has become an established methodology for achieving rigorous,
109 transparent and objective analysis of all evidence relating to the assessment task, with a wide
110 uptake by national and international risk assessment agencies including [the U.S. Environmental](#)
111 [Protection Agency US EPA](#) (EPA, 2022; EPA, 2023), [the European Food Safety Authority](#)
112 (EFSA, 2010; EFSA et al., 2017), and [the World Health Organization](#) (WHO, 2021). An
113 important part of systematic review methodology is assessing the internal validity of each

114 included study, i.e. the extent to which the design, conduct, and reporting of a study are likely to
115 have prevented bias or systematic error in its results or findings.

116 A challenge for systematic reviews that include *in vitro* studies, however, is that there is no
117 obviously authoritative (*i.e. generally accepted as valid*) tool suitable for assessing the internal
118 validity of this type of study. While several options exist for human and animal studies, [the](#)
119 development of a tool for *in vitro* studies is less advanced. ~~A number of tools have been~~
120 ~~developed but~~ three separate reviews have indicated that none of the existing [quality](#)
121 [assessment appraisal](#) tools for *in vitro* studies individually cover all critical aspects for assessing
122 the internal validity of *in vitro* studies (Barbosa et al., 2023; Tran et al., 2021; Whaley et al.,
123 2024). To address this issue, we are developing the INVITES-IN (IN VITro Experimental Studies
124 INternal validity) tool. To create a comprehensive and well-designed assessment tool for *in vitro*
125 studies, we are following the general framework for developing quality assessment tools as
126 suggested by Whiting et al. (2017) and our rigorous development protocol [is](#) described in
127 Mathisen et al. (2023) [and](#) Svendsen et al. (2023).

128 ~~Our development protocol describes~~ four methodological stages that we refer to as “studies”
129 [are described in the development protocols](#):

- 130 • Study [One](#)~~4~~: Creation of a comprehensive database (“item bank”) of concepts that may be
131 relevant for the assessment of internal validity of *in vitro* toxicity [testing](#) studies, [completed in](#)
132 [2023 of any](#) (Vist et al., 2024). ~~The item bank was derived from literature sources including~~
133 ~~study appraisal tools for human, animal, and in vitro studies, and statements from 20 in vitro~~
134 ~~experts participating in three focus group discussions.~~
- 135 • Study [Two](#)~~2 (the present study)~~: Identification [of items](#) of importance for the assessment of
136 internal validity in an *in vitro* study [from the item bank \(Study One\)](#) ~~(the present study)~~.
- 137 • Study [Three](#)~~3~~: Creation of a beta version of INVITES-IN based on the outcome of [S](#)studies
138 [One and Two](#)~~1 and 2~~.
- 139 • Study [Four](#)~~4~~: Creation of the final version of INVITES-IN, incorporating insights gained from
140 user-testing of the beta version.

141 The literature sources in [S](#)study [One](#)~~4~~ included a purposive sample of study appraisal tools
142 (Cooper et al., 2016; EPA, 2022; Higgins et al., 2024; NTP OHAT, 2015; Roth et al., 2021;
143 Sterne et al., 2019) and an item bank (Whaley et al., 2024). In total, ~~40597~~ items were included

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144 in the item bank. ~~After removal of 92 duplicates (the same item was collected from more than~~
 145 ~~one source), the number of unique items in the item bank was 405. It should be noted that items~~
 146 ~~included in the bank may still be equivalent, however, these were not removed in the~~
 147 ~~deduplication process because we aimed to preserve even small nuanced conceptual~~
 148 ~~differences.~~ To structure the item bank, items were organised thematically into twelve bias
 149 domains, such as detection, performance, and selection bias (the bias domains and definitions
 150 are available in Table 2).

151 ~~The goal of the study was to generate the final dataset of items from which the beta version of~~
 152 ~~INVITES-IN will be derived in Study Three.~~ The present paper describes the methods and
 153 results for ~~S~~study ~~2, Two~~ i.e., the process for narrowing down the 405 items in the item bank
 154 (~~study 1 Study One~~) by identifying the items that are of importance for assessment of internal
 155 validity of *in vitro* studies. The methods and results for ~~S~~study ~~One~~4 are described in Vist et al.
 156 (2024), and ~~studies 3 Study Three and Study Four and 4~~ will be described in a third manuscript.

157 ~~The present study was performed to identify prioritise from the Study One item bank itemsthe~~
 158 ~~for consideration which should be considered when assessing the potential for bias in an in vitro~~
 159 ~~study. The goal of the study was to generate the final dataset of items from which the~~
 160 ~~beta version of INVITES-IN is to will be derived in study 3. (Note that Kkey technical terms such~~
 161 as "item" are defined in the glossary at the end of this manuscript.)

162 2 Methods

163 2.1 Study design

164 A modified Delphi method (Dalkey and Helmer, 1963) was applied to identify the items in the
 165 item bank (Vist et al., 2024) that are of importance when assessing the potential for bias in an *in*
 166 *vitro* study. The Delphi method was chosen for its ability to collect subjective expert statements
 167 anonymously, promoting transparency while minimising the influence of social dynamics or
 168 individual personalities on the feedback process.

169 The study included a two-round quantitative digital Delphi survey followed by online Delphi
 170 panel workshops with discussions guided by a moderator from the project team discussions
 171 (referred to as a "workshop" in the protocol). The Delphi panel discussions workshops were used
 172 to ~~discuss and~~ obtain agreement on items that did not achieve agreement in the two-round
 173 Delphi survey. Each item was discussed in one Delphi panel, and pParticipants were invited to
 174 one guided Delphi panel workshop discussion each. Three guided Delphi panel discussions

workshops were arranged in total to enable smaller-group discussions on the items to make it possible to involve all participants in the discussions.

A Delphi round was defined as the process in which the participants completed a questionnaire. Participants had to complete the previous Delphi round to be eligible for the next, and both Delphi rounds to be eligible for participation in the online guided Delphi panel discussion workshop. The data analysis was performed after each Delphi round and after the Delphi panel discussions workshop. The participants received information about the results of each Delphi round as preparation for the next round or the Delphi panel discussion workshop.

2.2 Participants

To identify items of importance for the assessment of internal validity in an *in vitro* study, we considered it to be important that the participants have experience with both *in vitro* studies and systematic review principles. The research team and the scientific advisory group (see “Project Governance” section) nominated persons fulfilling the eligibility criteria defined in the protocol (Svendsen et al., 2023):

- Active in the field of *in vitro* studies (having practical experience in conducting *in vitro* studies or experience in analysing or evaluating data from such studies).
- Experience with systematic literature review principles (since the assessment of internal validity is an important part of the systematic review approach).
- Affiliation in academia, governmental institutions (including risk assessment institutions and research institutes) or private research institutes.
- Qualification at a post-doctoral level or higher.
- At least level B1 in English (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages level).

Participants in the focus group discussions in Study One were not eligible for participation in the Delphi study.

Thirty-seven eligible experts were nominated, and all were invited to participate in the Delphi study. They were contacted via email and received a letter of information (Supplementary materials 1). The recruitment period was September 2023 to October 2023. All participants who accepted the invitation ($N = 19$) actively confirmed their consent to participate in the study and were asked to fill out a short questionnaire to map geographical distribution, gender distribution, and experience level. Only two persons in the research team knew the identity of the

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206 participants, the one inviting [the](#) participants to the study (GHM) and the one creating the Delphi
207 questionnaires (CS).

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208 2.3 The Delphi survey questionnaire

209 All items in the [item](#) bank were included in the questionnaire. One duplicate item was not
210 discovered before the start of the Delphi study; therefore, 406 items were included in the Delphi
211 survey. The questionnaire for Delphi round two included the items that did not reach agreement
212 in round 1 (see Section 2.4 for criteria for identification of agreement).

213 The two-round Delphi survey was administered through Welphi (www.welphi.com), an online
214 survey platform designed for Delphi studies. Instructions (which summarise how information
215 was presented to the participants), the survey, and contact information for the project lead were
216 provided to the participants (Supplementary materials 2). Pilot testing of the survey was
217 performed by a minimum of four persons in the research team before the start of both rounds.
218 [Ideally, pilot testing would have been conducted with a sample of the population for whom the](#)
219 [survey was designed. Due to limited access to the intended sample, we opted to conduct the](#)
220 [pilot with members of the project team.](#)

221 Participants were automatically assigned participation codes randomly generated by the Welphi
222 platform. The research team did not have a key to link the participants to the participant codes,
223 thus, all responses were anonymised to all team members.

224 2.4 Rounds one and two

225 At the start of a round, participants received an email with a link to the survey. [The Welphi](#)
226 [software allowed the participants to log in and work with](#) ~~Participants were able to return to the~~
227 survey as many times as needed until the closure of the round. Round one was open from
228 December 13, 2023, to January 24, 2024. Round two lasted from February 29, 2024, to April 1,
229 2024. Two reminder emails were sent in the first round, and one reminder email was sent in the
230 second round.

231 In both rounds, participants were requested to rate each item according to the statement “*This*
232 *item should be considered when assessing the potential for bias in an in vitro study*” using a 5-
233 point Likert scale (“strongly disagree”, “somewhat disagree”, “neither agree nor disagree”,
234 “somewhat agree”, and “strongly agree”). Participants had the opportunity to include comments
235 and suggest alternative wording of the items. In round one, participants could also suggest

236 additional bias domains and items. For each item included in round two, ratings and comments
 237 provided in round one were visible for all participants. Each participant could also see their own
 238 ratings from round one. We only defined “bias” for the participants as systematic error, leaving it
 239 open to them how to interpret the importance of an item for introducing bias into an *in vitro*
 240 study. Also, participants were recommended not spending too long time on a single item. This
 241 was to capture their intuitive ratings of the items. Since we are interested in the aggregate
 242 answers of the group, intuitive ratings are sufficient.

243 The criteria for identification of agreement on the importance of an item for assessment of the
 244 risk of bias in *in vitro* studies were ~~pre~~defined in the protocol (Svendsen et al., 2023):

- 245 • ~~Agreement for inclusion of a~~An item ~~is included in INVITES-IN is identified~~ when at least
 246 70% of the participants “somewhat agree” and/or “strongly agree” with the statement.
- 247 • ~~Agreement for exclusion of an item from INVITES-IN an item is excluded is identified~~ when
 248 at least 70% of the participants “somewhat disagree” and/or “strongly disagree” with the
 249 statement.
- 250 • ~~An item that meets neither threshold for inclusion or exclusion is advanced to the next round~~
 251 ~~of Delphi, i.e. round two or the~~ guided Delphi panelworkshop discussions.

252 The analysis of survey data was blinded, ~~i.e. since the participant~~ responses were anonymised
 253 ~~to the investigators analysing the survey data. to all research team members.~~ The results from
 254 the first round were analysed by three investigators (GEV, HMA, PW), and items that did not
 255 reach agreement were included in the questionnaire for the second round. The results from the
 256 second round were analysed by three investigators (GEV, GHM, PW), and items that did not
 257 reach agreement were included in the guided Delphi panel discussionsworkshop.

258 Some items that marginally reached the numerical threshold for agreement in round one or
 259 round two were still included in round 2 and/or discussed in a ~~the~~ Delphi panelworkshop. This
 260 was a subjective decision made by the team when they were not confident that agreement had
 261 truly been reached (i.e. there was a risk of “false agreement”), even though the agreement rule
 262 was technically satisfied. Examples of this included when participant comments contradicted
 263 their ratings, or the distribution of responses (indicated using Excel Sparkline charts, as shown
 264 in Supplemental Material 3, sheet 5) suggested to the team a potential lack of consensus that
 265 should be explored in the next round of the consensus process. An overview of the participant
 266 ratings and comments as well as the team judgements (includes judgements on potential “false”
 267 agreements) are included in Supplementary materials 3.

268 2.5 The [guided Delphi panel discussionsworkshop](#)

269 Prior to the [guided Delphi panel discussionsworkshop](#), participants received the list of items
270 where agreement was not achieved, as well as all comments for these items from rounds one
271 and two. [The items were grouped under bias domains, and the guided Delphi panel
272 discussionworkshops were structured so each domain was fully discussed. This allowed
273 discussion of all items with ambiguous agreement.](#)

274 [Using Microsoft Teams](#), three 90-minute online [guided Delphi panel discussionworkshops](#) with
275 three to five participants each were held on May 7, 13 and 16 ~~using Microsoft Teams~~, to enable
276 in-depth discussion. The [guided Delphi panelworkshop](#) discussions were audio-recorded and
277 machine-transcribed using the transcribe function in Microsoft Teams classic (May 2024). Each
278 [Delphi panelworkshop](#) had a guided discussion on approximately one third of the items for
279 which no agreement had been identified. During the discussion, participants were asked to give
280 reasonings for why an item should or should not be considered when assessing the potential
281 for bias in an *in vitro* study. The [guided Delphi panel discussionworkshops](#) were moderated by
282 one investigator (PW), assisted by another (GEV), and notes were taken by a third (GHM). The
283 results were analysed by two investigators, and identification of agreement on importance was
284 based on the investigators judgement (GEV, PW). [Based on the issues and arguments raised in
285 the discussion with the Delphi panelworkshop participants, the two investigators decided
286 whether the item in question should be included or excluded.](#) Transcripts from the [guided Delphi
287 panelworkshop discussions](#) are available in Supplementary materials 5.

288 2.6 Deviations from the protocol

289 The Welphi software was used to prepare the Delphi surveys instead of using an Excel form as
290 it included several functions considered to be important, such as e.g. anonymising the Delphi
291 participants to the research team members and providing the ratings and comments from round
292 one to all participants in round two.

293 In the data analysis of the results from rounds one and two, three investigators evaluated the
294 agreement scores and comments to detect "false agreement" (see Section 2.4). When there
295 was uncertainty related to the agreement score, the item was brought forward to the next step to
296 receive additional rating and/or information from the participants.

297 [The average group response and the distribution of the participant ratings of each item are
298 presented in Supplementary materials 3. The median, standard deviation and the interquartile](#)

range are not reported, because the distribution of the participant ratings was considered more informative to detect potential "false agreement".

The deadlines for completing the surveys was more than the planned two weeks, were extended beyond two weeks, as suggested in the protocol, because the number of items included in the surveys was greater than originally anticipated.

3 Results

3.1 Participants and response rate

About 50.51% (19/37) of the invited participants accepted the invitation. One person-participant withdrew before the study was started due to personal reasons. The participant response rates were 94% (17/18) and 88% (15/17) for rounds one and two of the Delphi survey, respectively. Eighty-seven percent (87%) (13/15) of participants participated in a Delphi panel discussion workshop.

The characteristics of the fifteen-15 participants completing both rounds one and two are shown in Table 1. More than two thirds of the participants were female. Most participants were from Europe (60%) and North America (33%), 73% were female. Most participants had having extensive expertise with *in vitro* studies (80%). Experience with systematic review methods was more varied, 33%-percent reported some experience, 27%-percent reported moderate experience, and 40%-percent reported extensive experience.

Table 1. Characteristics of the 15 participants completing Delphi rounds one and two.

Characteristics	Number [n (%)]
<i>Geographical distribution</i>	
Europe	9 (60%)
North America	5 (33%)
South America	1 (7%)
<i>Gender</i>	
Female	11 (73%)
Male	4 (27%)
<i>Years of experience with in vitro studies</i>	
No experience	0 (0%)
1-3 years	2 (13%)

4-6 years	1 (7%)
More than 6 years	12 (80%)
<i>Experience with systematic review methods</i>	
No experience	0 (0%)
Some experience	5 (33%)
Moderate experience	4 (27%)
Extensive experience	6 (40%)

318

319 3.2 The item flow through the Delphi study

320 The Delphi process is shown in Figure 1. The results are available in .xlsx format (Microsoft
 321 Excel) in Supplementary Materials 3. This file consists of the dataset of items identified to be
 322 important for the assessment of the internal validity in *in vitro* studies (sheet 1), the full list of
 323 items included in the Delphi study (including all duplicates), with the agreement scores,
 324 investigator actions, and participant comments (sheet 2), the flow of items through the Delphi
 325 study presented per source (sheet 3), the flow of items through the Delphi study presented per
 326 bias domain (sheet 4), and the participant rating of the items in Delphi rounds one and two, and
 327 summary statistics for the ratings (sheet 5).

328 In the first round of the Delphi survey, 406 items were surveyed. Of these, 168 were included, 0
 329 items were excluded, 0 new items were suggested, and 0 items were revised. In round two, 238
 330 items were surveyed. Of these, 72 items were included, and 0 items were excluded. 166 items
 331 were then discussed in the Delphi panels, of which 33 items were excluded (1 duplicate item
 332 included in error was also removed). This left a total of 373 items for inclusion in Study Three of
 333 the INVITES-IN development process. Of the 406 items in the survey for the first Delphi round,
 334 168 were included and 238 undecided. No new items were suggested by the participants, and
 335 none of the existing items were revised. The 238 items on which no consensus was reached in
 336 round 1, were included in the second round of the Delphi survey, in which 72 were included and
 337 none excluded. The 166 items for which no agreement was identified were discussed in the
 338 workshops. Based on these discussions, 133 items were considered important for the
 339 assessment of the potential for bias in an *in vitro* study, whereas 33 were excluded from the
 340 dataset that will be the starting point for the creation of INVITES-IN.

341

342 **Figure 1. A flow chart of the Delphi process for identifying important items for**
 343 **assessment of internal validity in *in vitro* studies.**

344 Figure 2 illustrates the flow of items through the Delphi study with information on the source of
 345 the items (literature or focus group discussions) and the grouping of the items into bias
 346 domains. The definitions of the bias domains are included in Table 2. The code for generating
 347 the Sankey plot in Figure 2 is available in Supplementary materials 4.

348 In addition to the overview presented in Figure 2, Overviews of the the number flow of items from
 349 each bias domain and each source, included in through the Delphi study, and the number of
 350 items per bias domain and source the participants agreed that should be/not should be
 351 considered when assessing potential for bias in an in vitro study, are shown in Tables 2 and 3,
 352 respectively. For all bias domains, with one exception, agreement that the items should be

353 considered when assessing the potential for bias in an *in vitro* study was identified for more than
 354 90% of the items included in the Delphi study. The exception was the bias domain “Choice-of-
 355 Question bias” for which 4 out of 5 items were excluded.

356 ROBINS-E, a tool for assessment of potential biases in results from epidemiological cohort
 357 studies, had the lowest percentage of inclusion of items extracted from a source (83%). The
 358 inclusion of items from the other literature sources ranged from 95 to 100%. The inclusion of
 359 items discovered in the focus group discussions in Study One were 91% (the ~~item~~ number of
 360 items for all bias domains are available in Table 2, the ~~item~~ number of items for all tools
 361 sources are available in Table 3).

362

363

364
 365 **Figure 2. Flow of items considered through the Delphi process, disaggregated by source**
 366 **and bias domain. The flow of items from each source, mapped onto the bias domains, through**
 367 **the results from Delphi round one (R1), Delphi round two (R2) and the guided Delphi panel**
 368 **discussions/workshop (Workshop W). FGD: Focus group discussions. For source information**
 369 **and citations, see Table 3.**

370 The Sankey Plot was generated using R packages: `openxlsx` (Schauberg and Walker, 2025),
 371 `ggplot2` (Wickham, 2016), `tidyverse` (Wickham et al., 2019), and a `qgsanky` package (Sjoberg,
 372 2024), which required installation of the `devtools` package (Wickham et al., 2022).

373 Table 2 shows the number of items considered in each stage of the Delphi process, organised
 374 by bias domain. For each domain except “choice of question bias”, over 90% of items were
 375 included as being important for assessing the potential for bias of an *in vitro* study. The bias
 376 domains and definitions are primarily taken from a prerelease version of the Scientific Evidence
 377 Code System (SEVCO) research methods ontology (Alper et al., 2021; FEvIR Platform Version

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378 0.80.0, 06.12.2022). We modified one SEVCO bias domain (changing “Early study termination
379 bias” SEVCO:00370 to “Timing of study termination bias”), and two bias domains added
380 (“Metabias” and “Other”). [Table 3 shows the number of items assessed in each stage of the](#)
381 [Delphi process, organised by source.](#)

382 **Table 2. Items ~~that should be considered~~ in the Delphi process, organised by bias domain, the potential for bias in an *in***
 383 **~~*vitro* study per bias domain.~~** The table shows the number of items included in the Delphi study and the number of these items that
 384 ~~were considered to be of importance for the assessment of the potential for bias in an *in vitro* study. The bias domains and definitions~~
 385 ~~were taken from the Scientific Evidence Code System (SEVCO) research methods ontology (Alper et al., 2021; FEvIR Platform~~
 386 ~~Version 0.80.0, 06.12.2022), with one SEVCO bias domain modified (“Timing of Study Termination Bias” changed from “Early study~~
 387 ~~termination bias” SEVCO:00370), and two bias domains added (“Metabias” and “Other”).~~

Bias domain	Definition	Items <u>considered</u> <u>assessed by the</u> Delphi participants (n)	Items <u>where the threshold for</u> <u>agreement on the importance of an</u> <u>item for assessment of the risk for</u> <u>bias in <i>in vitro</i> studies was</u> <u>reached</u> <u>included after the complete</u> <u>Delphi</u> .[n (%)]
Analysis bias	A bias related to the analytic process applied to the data.	55	51 (93%)
Attrition bias	A bias due to absence of expected participation or data collection after selection for study inclusion.	24	22 (92%)
Choice-of- Question bias	A bias in research design in which the research question (that the study is designed to answer) is inappropriate for the context.	5	1 (20%)
Conflicted interest bias	A bias in which decision makers influencing research design, conduct, analysis or reporting have goals or motivations that conflict with scientific research objectives.	8	8 (100%)

Confounding covariate bias	A situation in which the effect or association between an exposure or outcome is distorted by another variable. For confounding covariate bias to occur the distorting variable must be (1) associated with the exposure and the outcome, (2) not in the causal pathway between exposure and outcome, and (3) unequally distributed between the groups being compared.	7	7 (100%)
Detection bias	A bias due to distortions in any process involved in the determination of the recorded values for a variable.	104	97 (93%)
Metabias	A general distorting influence on investigator decision-making that may bias the results or findings of a study	29	28 (97%)
Other	A distortion in results due to factors other than those described in the SEVCO terms	5	5 (100%)
Performance bias	A bias resulting from differences between the received exposure and the intended exposure.	77	72 (94%)
Reporting bias	A bias due to distortions in the selection of or representation of information in study results or research findings.	18	18 (100%)
Selection bias	A bias resulting from methods used to select subjects or data, factors that influence initial study	70	60 (86%)

	participation, or differences between the study sample and the population of interest		
Timing of Study Termination bias	A bias due to the decision to end the study earlier or later than planned.	3	3 (100%)
Total (sum)		405	372

388

389 **Table 3. Items [considered in the Delphi process, organised by that should be considered when assessing the potential for](#)**
390 **[bias in an *in-vitro* study per source](#)**. Since some items were collected from more than one source, the total number of items in this
391 table is 497 (the number of items in the item bank before removal of duplicates).

Item sSource (-ID, overview of type of source)		Items considered assessed by the Delphi participants (n)	Items included after the complete Delphi [n (%)] items where the threshold for agreement on the importance of an item for assessment of the risk for bias in <i>in-vitro</i> studies was reached [n (%)]	Source Citation
Cooper	A study sensitivity assessment tool	21	21 (100%)	Cooper et al. (2016)
FGD	The Focus group discussions (Study One)	139	127 (91%)	Vist et al. (2024)
IRIS	An integrated risk information system	43	42 (98%)	EPA (2022)

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OHAT	A handbook for conducting systematic reviews for health effects evaluations	45	43 (96%)	NTP OHAT (2015)
ROB-2	Version 2 of the Cochrane risk-of-bias tool for randomized trials	48	46 (96%)	Sterne et al. (2019)
ROBINS-E	A tool to assess risk of bias in non-randomized follow-up studies of exposure effects	69	57 (83%)	Higgins et al. (2024)
SciRAP	A tool for evaluation of toxicity data for Risk Assessment and Policy	36	36 (100%)	Roth et al. (2021)
Whaley	An item bank for <i>in vitro</i> studies	96	91 (95%)	Whaley et al. (2024)

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393 4 Discussion

394 We ~~have~~ performed a two round digital Delphi survey followed by ~~an~~-online [Delphi](#)
 395 ~~panelworkshop with guided~~-discussions [guided by a moderator from the project team](#) to identify
 396 items that should be considered when assessing the potential for bias in an *in vitro* study. The
 397 INVITES-IN item bank (Vist et al., 2024), consisting of 405 items, was the basis for the [Delphi](#)
 398 study. The Delphi participants agreed that [372 \(92%\)](#) of these items should be considered when
 399 assessing the potential for bias in an *in vitro* study, ~~whereas only 33 not-should not be~~
 400 [considered](#).

401 4.1 Strengths and limitations of the Delphi study

402 4.1.1 Number of Delphi rounds

403 The workload for the Delphi participants was extensive, with 406 items included in the round
 404 one questionnaire and 238 in the round two questionnaire. Although Delphi rounds can be
 405 repeated until agreement among participants is reached, we decided to arrange [guided Delphi](#)
 406 ~~panelworkshops~~ for discussion of the items where agreement was not achieved in two Delphi
 407 rounds instead of including more Delphi rounds. This was partly because we considered it to be
 408 more efficient, and partly to avoid drop-outs since the surveys were long and time consuming.

409 4.1.2 Participants and response rates

410 Based on a study by Akins et al. (2005), [we considered](#) 15 participants ~~were-considered-to-be~~
 411 the minimum ~~number needed for our Delphi study (Svendson et al., 2023)~~. Most participants in
 412 this Delphi study were from Europe and North America (~~93%-percent~~). While better
 413 geographical inclusivity was desired, we are uncertain about the impact this has on the validity
 414 of our study. Most participants claimed to have extensive experience with *in vitro* studies,
 415 whereas the level of experience with systematic review methods was more varied, being fairly
 416 evenly distributed between "some", "moderate" and "extensive". We are unsure whether it would
 417 have had any effect on ~~the-our~~ [results](#) if more people had extensive systematic review
 418 experience.

419 It has been shown that long surveys [are likely to induce respondent fatigue and](#) reduce the
 420 response rates (Gargon et al., 2019; Jeong D. et al., 2023) which may explain the drop-out of
 421 three participants during round one and round two. We considered our response rates for Delphi
 422 round one and two on [94%](#) and ~~88%-percent~~, respectively, to be acceptable. According to Akins
 423 et al. (2005), based on healthcare Delphi study response rates found in the literature, a
 424 response rate of ~~70%-percent~~ [could be expected](#).

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425 Participation in a [guided Delphi panel discussionworkshop](#) was desired but not a requirement
 426 for participation in the Delphi study. We considered participation of 13 out of 15 Delphi
 427 participants in the follow-up [Delphi panel discussionsworkshop](#) to be a reasonable retention
 428 rate. Overall, while drop-outs did affect agreement scores and may have explained ~~some a~~
 429 ~~small number of~~ inclusion decisions, we do not believe drop-out rates had an important effect on
 430 the validity of our Delphi process.

431 [4.1.3 Threshold for agreement](#)

432 We acknowledge that the threshold value has a large impact on the identification of agreement.
 433 Webbe et al. (2023) demonstrated the importance of having predefined criteria for identification
 434 of consensus. Our criteria for identification of agreement on the importance of an item for
 435 assessment of the risk of bias in *in vitro* studies were ~~pre~~defined in the protocol (Svendsen et
 436 al., 2023). Also, Webbe et al. (2023) concluded that at present it is unclear whether an optimal
 437 definition of consensus criteria exists. The threshold for agreement was set relatively low for
 438 inclusion and relatively high for exclusion on the assumption that ~~the base level of consensus~~
 439 ~~disagreement~~ about the importance of a given item was likely to be ~~relatively low and highly~~
 440 ~~contingent on the specific experience and knowledge of a participant~~~~high,~~ ~~and~~ ~~such~~ that even
 441 half of participants agreeing an item is important would likely be enough that it should be
 442 considered in an eventual tool, ~~and~~ ~~while that potentially even~~ half of participants disagreeing
 443 that an item should be included should not necessarily be grounds for excluding it. ~~We believe~~
 444 ~~T~~his consideration, along with our understanding that our sample of experts is not
 445 comprehensive, ~~we feel~~~~feel it~~ justifies our inclusive thresholds.

446 [4.2 Applicability of concepts included in tools designed for assessment of human and animal](#) 447 [studies to *in vitro* studies](#)

448 We used assessment tools designed for humans and animal studies for the development of the
 449 item bank, based on the assumption that they may contain concepts that are applicable to *in*
 450 *vitro* studies (Vist et al., 2024). The applicability of concepts used for evaluation of risk of bias
 451 across different study types was also suggested in a report by the National Academies of
 452 Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (National Academies of Sciences and Medicine, 2023).
 453 Here, tool developers were recommended to ~~identify~~ ~~identify existing concepts used for~~
 454 ~~evaluation of~~ risk of bias ~~concepts from in~~ human and animal toxicity studies ~~that are applicable~~
 455 ~~to other types of toxicity testing methods~~ and to use these in the development of approaches for
 456 evaluation ~~of risk of bias in~~ other study types. Although the items will need to be interpreted to
 457 precisely match the *in vitro* appraisal context in the final INVITES-IN tool, the high proportion of

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458 retained items in the Delphi study from the different item bank sources (83% - 100%; Table 3)
459 supports the assumption ~~of applicability of that~~ concepts used for evaluation of risk of bias are
460 applicable across different study types.

461 4.3 Coverage of items of importance for validity assessment of *in vitro* studies by existing tools

462 More than 100 of the 405 items in the item bank were not found in the literature sources
463 sampled but were identified by 20 *in vitro* experts during focus group discussions in Study One
464 (Vist et al., 2024). Some examples of items identified in the focus group discussions included
465 “Method for fitting curves to data”, “Set of reference chemicals”, and “Adjustment for cellular
466 growth rates between groups”. The present study shows that a different group of experts agreed
467 that more than 90% of these new items are important for the assessment of the potential for
468 bias in an *in vitro* study.

469 While it is theoretically possible that a fully comprehensive tool for assessment of the internal
470 validity of *in vitro* studies already exists, three existing systematic reviews (Barbosa et al., 2023;
471 Tran et al., 2021; Whaley et al., 2024) have not found one and nobody involved in our project
472 (either project team or advisory board) we are aware of one. It therefore seems improbable
473 unlikely that a literature sampling strategy on its own is likely to be sufficient for ensuring
474 comprehensive coverage of relevant concepts when developing an internal validity assessment
475 tool. Given the practical challenges of comprehensively reviewing the literature, we believe it is
476 a sound pragmatic choice for tool developers to supplement purposive literature samples with
477 focus group discussions. We believe the high rate of retention of items from focus groups
478 through the Delphi process supports this choice.

479 4.4 Elimination of few items by Delphi

480 Strikingly few items (n=33) were eliminated by our Delphi process. One explanation is that our
481 Delphi process might have retained items of low relevance for assessing the internal validity of
482 *in vitro* toxicity studies, due to a combination of our inclusive threshold for retaining items , a
483 lengthy process likely to have induced respondent fatigue (Jeong et al., 2023), and a possible
484 tendency for items that were confusing to participants not being eliminated.

485 As we discussed in section 4.2, we view the inclusive-relatively low threshold for agreement we
486 view as desirable. The length of the survey, given the number of items, seems unavoidable. In
487 terms of confusion, it is clear from Delphi comments and scores that participants were unclear
488 as to what many items meant. Also, the similarity across some items may have been
489 challenging for the participants. As investigators, we believe this is a consequence of

490 participants being presented with decontextualized items in the absence of a specific task.
 491 When discussed in the [Delphi panelsworkshop](#), with the possibility to explore what the items
 492 mean, agreement was more readily attainable. ~~Also, the similarity across some items may have~~
 493 ~~been challenging for the participants.~~

494 On the other hand, it may anyway be expected that the retention rate for items would be high.
 495 ~~since~~ The item bank sources already represent a degree of expert consensus about what
 496 matters in terms of introduction of bias to studies, and it therefore seems ~~probable~~ likely that a
 497 separate group of experts ~~is likely to~~ would agree with the experts who made the original tools
 498 and participated in the focus groups.

499 4.5 Lessons learned and recommendations for tool developers

500 The overall goal of this project is the development of a tool for assessment of internal validity of
 501 *in vitro* studies. We have aggregated a large number of existing concepts from the literature as
 502 well as developed some novel concepts from the focus groups, and all are included in an item
 503 bank (Vist et al., 2024). The overall aim of this study was to identify the items that should be
 504 considered when developing the tool. To this end, we expected that the 405 items in the item
 505 bank would be reduced by the Delphi process to a smaller set of key items. This did not occur,
 506 and we only eliminated ~~eight percent~~ 8% of the items.

507 [The fact that we eliminated few items, the participant confusion about being presented with](#)
 508 [decontextualised items in a written survey, and the theoretical reason for expecting agreement](#)
 509 [rate on items to be high, in combination suggests that applying a Delphi process to an item bank](#)
 510 [may not be the most efficient way to move forward in designing a bias assessment tool.](#) If we
 511 were to repeat this exercise, instead of using a Delphi process to select items for inclusion in the
 512 tool we ~~instead recommend~~ would first analyse ~~ing~~ the concepts represented by the items in the
 513 item bank, interpreting the results into study appraisal criteria, and then subject the appraisal
 514 criteria to a Delphi process. For INVITES-IN, the concepts will be analysed in ~~s~~Study [Three](#)
 515 before the draft tool is created, and participants in the focus groups (in ~~S~~study [One](#)) will be
 516 invited to give feedback on the draft tool before the user testing in ~~S~~study [Four](#). [The creation of](#)
 517 [the item bank itself, especially if it includes focus group discussions, remains highly valuable.](#)

518 5 Conclusion

519 ~~In this study,~~ [Of 405 items, 372 were agreed on by the Delphi process as being important expert](#)
 520 [agreement that ninety two percent of the items in the item bank should be considered](#) when
 521 assessing the potential for bias in an *in vitro* study ~~were identified~~. Thus, the Delphi process only

522 eliminated a low number of items. The 372 retained items will be interpreted into a manageable
523 set of study appraisal criteria and a supporting guidance that will constitute the INVITES-IN
524 study appraisal tool.

525 Our work supports the contention that many items included in tools designed for the
526 assessment of the internal validity of human and animal studies are broadly applicable to the
527 assessment of *in vitro* studies. Our work also supports the contention that a purely literature-
528 based approach to identifying bias items is unlikely to be comprehensive, and that the use of
529 focus group discussions with experts is a pragmatic and valuable approach to increasing
530 coverage of items in a tool development process.

531 In conclusion, this study demonstrates the value of using rigorous methods to ensure a
532 comprehensive dataset as the starting point for creation of an assessment tool.

533 [Project governance](#)

534 This study is part of the project “Next Generation Risk Assessment in Practice” (VKM, 2023),
535 included in the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC)
536 ([PARC, 2023](#)). A research team is responsible for the creation of INVITES-IN. A scientific
537 advisory group consisting of experts in methods for tool development, systematic review
538 methods, chemical risk assessment, toxicology, and/or *in vitro* models has been established to
539 provide the research team with strategic guidance and support during the process of creating
540 INVITES-IN (VKM, 2023).

541 [Definitions /Glossary](#)

542 These definitions have been updated since publication of our study protocol (Svendsen et al.,
543 2023).

544 **Bias** is a systematic error, or deviation from the truth, in the results or findings of individual
545 studies or across studies. Systematic error may be introduced through limitations in the design,
546 conduct, or reporting of a study.

547 **Bias domains** are a conceptual framework for [thematically](#) organising the limitations in conduct,
548 design, or reporting of a study that [have affected](#)[may affect](#) the internal validity of a study. Bias
549 domains in the present study include but are not limited to detection, performance, and selection
550 bias.

551 **Internal validity** is the extent to which the design, conduct, and reporting of a study ~~are~~is likely
552 to have prevented bias.

553 **Items** are linguistically minimalist expressions of study assessment concepts. In the INVITES-IN
554 tool development methodology, "items" are derived ~~by a normalisation process~~ from study
555 assessment criteria ~~presented-collected from in~~-study appraisal tools and ~~described in~~ focus
556 group discussions, that potentially relate to the internal validity of an *in vitro* study.

557 **Item bank** is a database of items.

558 **Risk of bias** is the potential for systematic error in the results or findings of a study or across
559 studies. Tools for assessing the internal validity of studies tend to focus on risk of bias, as bias
560 itself cannot usually be directly measured.

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569 Data Protection Impact Assessment has been performed and was approved by Norwegian
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572 ~~biological materials or information on health were collected.~~

573 Declaration of interests

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